

UV-C CABINET WORKFLOW

! The steps outlined below are an example of UV-C cabinet implementation; workflow may be modified to the local context and should be approved by relevant regulatory bodies. No warranties are implied and workflows are used at your own risk. "Mask" denotes N95 respirator. This method may possibly be used for surgical masks, however data on surgical mask decontamination via UV-C and impact on surgical mask performance are sparse - results on bioburden reduction are preliminary, internal, and unpublished. PPE & hand hygiene best practices must be followed at all times. Additional information available at covidppeguide.com/uvc-decon.

MASK DROPOFF

1 LABEL NEW MASK AND DON MASK

2 AFTER CLINICAL SHIFT, DOFF AND INSPECT MASK

3 CHECK TALLY (<5) AND PACK IN CLEAN CONTAINER

4 DISINFECT CONTAINER EXTERIOR & MARKER. PERFORM HAND HYGIENE

5 LOG IN MASK

6 LOAD CART AND TRANSPORT TO DECON AREA

MASK REPROCESSING

7 UNPACK AND CHECK MASK
Disinfect dirty containers after unpacking

8 LOAD RACK
Ensure no contact between masks, no shadowing on mask surfaces

9 PLACE RACK IN CABINET

11 VERIFY DOSE WITH CYCLE TIME AND/ OR SENSOR

10 CLOSE DOOR AND SWITCH ON
Safety check: cabinet well sealed and doors locked

12 SWITCH OFF. OPEN AND UNLOAD RACKS

13 WIPE STRAPS AND ADD TALLY
Perform secondary decontamination of straps with appropriate disinfectant. Do not wipe facepiece.

14 PACK AND LABEL CLEAN CONTAINERS
Match user details on N95 and container

MASK PICKUP

15 CHECK HCW NAME AND RETRIEVE MASK
Disinfect reusable containers

16 EXAMINE MASK FOR
• Damage
• Soiling
• Number of cycles

17 LOG OUT MASK

18 DON MASK. PERFORM HAND HYGIENE BEFORE AND AFTER DONNING MASK

19 LEAVE AREA

